

BEE-STEWARD

Table 1. Maximum number and date of bumblebee colonies and pollinators in year 5 and the change in maximum numbers of Colonies and Pollinators from year 1 to 5 as a percentage (trend).

My Map	Colonies			Pollinators			key
	max	date	trend (%)	max	day	trend (%)	
Example_Farm_Baseline	7	07-Apr	-30	100	03-Jun	-31	
Example_Farm_plot	33	04-May	194	377	26-May	96	

Figure 1. Colonies (a) and pollinators (b) (mean) over final 3 years (error bars = Standard Error).

Figure 2. Number of bumblebee colonies over 5 years.

Figure 3. Number of bumblebee pollinators over 5 years.